

EVALUATION OF TEACHERS' OPINIONS RELATING IMPROVING QUALIFICATION IN TEACHING PROCESSⁱ

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Abstract:

Improving quality and providing permanent learning in the teaching process undoubtedly depend on the time that teacher spends and active and voluntary participation of students. This study is important for providing perspectives about new techniques and suggestions to the teachers and related persons by determining actions and thoughts of teachers relating teaching process. Aim of the research is to determine teachers' actions for increasing the quality of teaching process. The research was carried out by using screening model to determine the actions of subject-matter teacher, working in Tokat province, for increasing the quality in teaching. 50 primary and middle school teachers attended to the research, working in Tokat central district and filling out the form voluntarily in interview. 12 open-ended questions weren't evaluated due to several missing information. Convenience sampling method was used in the research, one of the qualitative research techniques. The convenience sampling technique brings speed, easy implementation and economy. Six (6) open-ended questions addressed to 50 voluntary teachers to determine the opinions of teachers about increasing the quality of teaching process. Before the final form of the open-ended questionnaire, opinions of 2 specialists who have doctoral degree in Department of Curriculum and Instruction were obtained, and 5 subject-matter teachers who didn't include in study group were implemented pretesting. Questionnaire with open-ended questions were designed and participants were asked to write their opinions in the form and send e-mails to researcher including the forms. In this method, participants were asked to answer the questions as they were asked in the interview. These answers were supposed to be in written form. Questions used to determine teachers' opinions

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are as follows: 1. What does it mean to be an active student in teaching process? How do you evaluate this? 2. What can be done to make students active in teaching process? 3. How do you keep alive student's interest (voluntary participation without boredom)? 4. How do you support permanent learning? 5. How do you support motivation? 6. Which activities do you implement activities to improve quality of teaching process? Content analysis method was used, one of the qualitative data analysis. In the process of reporting the data, reliability was attempted to increase by quoting teachers' opinions directly. Participants were coded as TE1, TE2... In order to increase reliability, two researchers randomly coded 5 open-ended questions; coefficient of coincidence was computed .76 by using "agreeing/agreeing & disagreeing" formula. Findings were organized under the seven themes: motivation, active student, teacher, providing permanent learning, features of teaching environment, method, technique and restraining student's activity.

Keywords: teaching process, quality of teaching, motivation, teachers' opinion

1. Introduction

Students, the most important participants of teaching-learning process, should be actively participating in teaching process in order to reach desired knowledge, ability, attitude and behavior. Increasing the quality of teaching process and the effort spent to support permanent learning depends on active and voluntary participation. It is necessary to improve the quality of the teaching process in order to improve the quality of education and students' success. This cannot be achieved without qualified teachers (Seferoğlu, 2004).

Azar (2011) emphasized that evaluation of teaching training system is necessary for training teacher with quality and quantity as today's required. There is demand in education, from pre-school to higher education, though; practices that will improve the quality of education haven't been implemented. Education programs that are appropriate for society and business world haven't been improved, and appropriate teaching cannot be provided. It can be say that an education system improving student's creativity and ability hasn't been established. In Turkey, an education system focusing on memorization and central examination has been adopted. According to Turkish Education Association, Education Evaluation Report 2014, Turkey is 21th in productivity index including 30 OECD countries, cannot use properly its sources. (p.89) Teacher is the key to the teaching-learning process. That's why, it is important to determine what and how teachers do. From point of view of this, the main issue is to determine what is wrong or right in teaching implementations by considering teachers'

opinions. Also, it is important to provide new perspectives to teachers and respective about new implementations and suggestions by determining what teachers do and what teachers think in order to adopt an effective teaching process. In today's education system, there are crucial problems stated by teachers and administrators: active participation of students, maintaining students' motivation and interests. Efforts have been made to enlighten these points in this study; it is aimed to determine what the teachers do in order to adopt an effective teaching process.

2. Method

The research was conducted with screening model to determine what subject matter teachers do to improve the teaching quality. It is aimed to describe the situation, subject to screening model, in its circumstances and as it is. There is no effort to alter or influence the events. The important thing is to describe situations appropriately (Karasar, 2005). The research was conducted with screening model and data were obtained using open-ended questions.

2.1 Study Group

Study group consisted of 38 teachers working in Tokat province in 2015-2016 academic year. Appropriate sampling method was used for some reasons such as easy accessibility, speed, ease of implementation and economic efficiency. Teachers were interviewed at schools in central district on between 1 - 15 March, and 62 voluntary teachers received e-mails; 50 of them answered e-mails they received. However, 12 open ended questionnaires were excluded from analysis due to various missing information. After teachers were interviewed on between 1 – 20 April, participants' properties were written in Table 1. Gender, fields, school types, seniority and ages of participant are written in Table 1.

Table 1: Properties of Teacher

Gender	Number
Man	20
Woman	18
Total	38
Fields of Teachers	
Primary School Teacher	13
English	12
Maths	2
Science	2
Turkish	2
Others (Religion-1,music-1, pre-school-1, chemistry-1, philosophy-1, history-1, social studies-1)	7
Total	38
Type of the School	
Primary	15
Middle	14
Highschool	9
Total	38
Seniority	
2 - 5 years	15
6 - 10 years	13
11 -15 years	6
16 years and over	4
Total	38
Age	
20-25	4
26-30	13
31-35	10
36-40	7
41-45	4
Total	38

2.2. Data Collecting Tools

Data were collected from 50 voluntary teachers, pre-interviewed, through e-mail and six (6) open-ended questions. Participants were asked to write their opinions in the open-ended questionnaires, and send the questionnaires through e-mail. In this method, participants were asked to give answers as they did in the interview. However, these answers were given in written form (Creswell, 2005). 6 open-ended questions, prepared by the researcher and sent through e-mails, were filled by five teachers who didn't participate in the study group for the purpose of pretesting. The final draft was formed after required corrections. Questions in questionnaire used to determine teachers' opinions are as follows: 1.What does active student mean student in teaching process? How do you evaluate this? 2. What can be done to make students active in teaching process? 3. How do you keep alive student's interest (voluntary participation without boredom)? 4. How do you support permanent learning? 5. How do you

support motivation? 6. Which activities do you implement activities to improve quality of teaching process?

2.3. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed by using content analysis method. Content analysis requires to examine closer the data obtained and to reach concepts and themes that explain this data (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2008). Participants' opinions were collected through open-ended questionnaire. The opinions were transferred to the electronic environment (raw data consists of 20 pages and 9020 words in word format, in Times New Roman, single line 12 font size). In analysis the collected data, these stages were followed: coding the data, finding the themes, organizing the codes and themes, describing and interpreting the findings. In the process of reporting the data, reliability was attempted to increase by quoting teachers' opinions directly. Participants were coded as TE1, TE2... In order to increase reliability, two researchers randomly coded 5 open-ended questions; coefficient of coincidence was computed by using "agreeing/agreeing+disagreeing" formula. Coefficient of coincidence between the two coders was computed .76.

3. Findings

In this section, categorization and interpretation of the themes and codes according to the content analysis of the data collected in the research. Teachers' opinions were analyzed under seven themes in total.

Table 2: The list of Themes and Codes Created by Using Teachers' Opinions Relating Improving the Quality in Teaching Process

Theme	Code	Number of views
1-Motivation	1-Motivation for Lessons	6
	2-Motivation and Teacher	18
	3-Rewarding Learning	11
2-Active Student	1-Active Student	30
	1-Specialitie of Teacher	17
3-Teacher	2-Supporting Student	7
	3-Knowing Student	4
	4-Attitude of Teacher	7
	1-Associating with Daily Life	5
4-Providing Permanent Learning	2-Ways of Ensuring Permanent Learning	12
	3-Practice and Transferring to Real Life	10
	4-Repetition	16
	1-Features of Education Environment	8
5-Education Environment	1-Method - Material	17
	2-Activity	14
6-Method and Technique	1- Preventing Student Activeness	6
7-Restraining Student Activeness		

3.1. Motivation

Teachers' opinions were analyzed under three sub-code, relating motivation: motivation for lessons, motivation and teacher, rewarding student.

3.1.1. Motivation for Lessons

This section includes sample teachers' quotations relating motivating students.

T6: *"...First of all, it requires to take student's or students' attention to create interest and will. Later, some ways may be tried to endear the lesson. Activities, appropriate for student's age, can be used before starting the lesson."*

T9: *"...It is necessary to make student ready and willing. I try to motivate the student by ensuring the student believes and by stating she/he can find the truth with the help of the mistakes."*

T26: *"I always keep the teaching process alive. I make movements, mimics, eye movements and I change my voice to keep their attention alive. I bring materials that I'm sure they've never seen before and surprise them to raise their excitement. This increases the level they focus on the lesson."*

T33: *"Keeping their attention alive with question answer method"*

T31: *"Giving striking, interesting examples they can experience"*

T36: *"I inform them; I give examples from my life. I talk about successful scientists and businessmen/women, and raise their interest."*

Teachers stated that they increase the interest by raising interest and will, endearing the lesson, doing appropriate activities that students like, making them to believe that they can do, keeping the teaching process alive, keeping their attention with talking and mimics. Apart from these, teachers use surprise materials, keep students' attention alive with question-answer, give striking interesting examples they can experience in real life, giving examples from lives of successful scientists and businessmen/women, and increase and maintain their attention.

3.1.2. Motivation and Teacher

Some of the teachers' opinions relating methods they use to motivate their students are as follows:

T1: *"Providing self-confidence to students, considering students' interest and motivation in advance, evoking the feel that student is valuable as an individual, talking about achievements will improve the teaching process."*

T4: *"I can use question-answer method, change my methods and create rich teaching environment to keep motivation alive."*

T5: *"I try to be nice and active in lesson. Smiling to students, to 5th and 6th grade, breaks their prejudice. Students who have positive thoughts about the lesson are successful. I call them by their name and say their characteristics."*

T7: *"I try to give students responsibilities they can fulfill so that they can feel success and study to do better. I express that I trust them and they can be successful if they study. I sometimes reward them."*

T10: *"Making students feel more valuable makes students successful. Motivation will appear when we encourage students to be more self-confident, and raise students with confidence."*

T12: *"I try to motivate them by exposing them with realities in their lives."*

T14: *"...That's why; I use more than one method to motivate students. Most of the time, I use reinforcements. We make deals for the end of the year. If they are successful, we take pictures together and eat cakes. Food they never taste becomes their gifts."*

T18: *"...I try to motivate students by creating a teaching environment in which they can feel comfortable and be active."*

T19: *"To motivate students, I encourage students by giving the questions that will be on the exams. I say to them they won't be successful if they don't pay attention to the subject, and talk about the importance of the subject. I also say to them that they have succeeded before, and they can be successful again if they want to be."*

T21: *"Providing motivation is half of learning. This is the issue we have difficulties the most. Creating motivation only in the classroom is also hard. Students' friends and parents should take part in this process. Teachers should show the feeling of success by appreciating the student and showing the student's strength. If a student believes that she/he can success, she/he is motivated."*

T23: *"I cannot motivate the student unless I know and empathize with him/her. At first, I try to know the student, and then I motivate him/her according to wishes and features."*

T24: *"By appreciating the student, talking about the things he/she can do, listening the student's aims and dreams, guiding the student and suggesting him/her to progress in the direction of his/her aims."*

T25: *"I appreciate the simple things student succeed, and making him/her to believe in himself/herself. Then, I appreciate the hard things the student succeed, and proceed step by step."*

T27: *"Every student's interest and motivation is different. What is important for the student, what the student likes, what the student doesn't like are determined, they can be considered when increasing the motivation."*

T28: *"By making them to like my lesson, and making them to wonder about my lesson."*

T34: *"By showing them that I care about them."*

T37: *“Providing an environment which is created according to students’ interest and abilities is one of the most impressive ways. A student feeling his/her interests are cared change his/her attitude towards the lesson and the teacher.”*

Teachers saying his/her opinions about providing motivation stated that they motivate the students by feeling students valuable, talking about achievements and how they will work in the future, changing the method, by mentioning about the students’ strength, showing them what success is like, rewarding the students, offering a comfortable learning environment, making students to like the lesson, encouraging the students, saying them they are successful, making them to believe that they can success.

3.1.3. Rewarding the Student

Some teachers’ opinions relating what they do to reward their students are as follows:

T2: *“... by creating a competitive environment, offering activities they can success, giving little gifts.”*

T3: *“Grade is very important for the student, especially for the successful one. That’s why, sometimes grading the students answering the correct answer to a question in the listening activity keeps the lesson alive and it makes students more active and motivated.”*

T4: *“I usually find daily and interesting questions about the students’ lives. I use problems that the students can experience in their lives. They do competitions activity and I give feedback to them. Students solving the problems take rewards such as a star or “well done”, and they can feel what the success is.”*

T13: *“We can use rewards and reinforces that can motive students in the teaching process. Also, giving feedbacks during the lesson makes students improve himself/herself and affects positively the motivation.”*

T15: *“... Computer, music, computer games... I reward the students variently. I give grades to the students attending the lesson. We choose student of the month.”*

T20: *“Motivation can be provided with small and symbolic weekly rewards.”*

T22: *“Variable gifts can be given to the students in order to make active them in the teaching process. I think the gifts that will be given should draw students’ interests.”*

T29: *“By making student active all the time, offering different gifts after the activities.”*

T30: *“By highlighting the success event it is small, showing students’ success as an example for the others, rewarding.”*

T33: *“By using visual materials more often, by using punishment and reward method.”*

T35: *“I reward their positive attitudes and behaviors. I make them to feel the difference between the student who fulfills his/her responsibilities and who doesn’t. (I control students regularly and record what students do.)”*

Teachers saying their opinions about rewarding the student stated that they reward students by doing activities which can increase the students' success, rewarding the successful students with grades, using daily and interesting problems, using rewards motivating the students, choosing student of the month.

3.2. Active Student

Teachers' opinions about features of an active student are written under the *active student* title.

3.2.1. Active Student

Some of the teachers' opinions about features of an active student are as follows:

T1: *"Precondition of being active is feeling comfortable. To provide that comfort, teacher creates a positive communication environment. Student likes his/her teacher and create positive attitude and thoughts towards the lesson over time. Teacher should use activities with the help of which student ask questions, criticize and creatively thinking. The key point in active participation is increase student's sense of wonder."*

T2: *"Forcing the teacher with the questions, establishing cause effect relationship, participating actively, suggesting new activities, being interested with the lessons, running after his/her wonder."*

T3: *"Being active means contributing lessons actively, talking in the lessons and asking questions. Directing, conducting the lesson, being a part of the lesson and arguing mean using the opportunity when moving from theory to practice."*

T4: *"Active student means the lesson is student and the class centered, which means the whole class participates in the lesson and participate in activities individually or as a group."*

T6: *"Active student in teaching process means involving the process and support it. Active student holds up his/her finger and participate during the lesson. If student fulfill the responsibilities (homework, project, etc.), focuses on the lesson and ensures meaningful learning, is with high motivation and attitude, is open to learn new things, we can talk about active involvement."*

T9: *"... participating the lesson with a preparation made before, involving the lesson with awareness, be guided counseled according to achievements."*

T10: *"It means that student participate in the lesson actively, and learns by practicing and experiencing. Also, it means increasing the student's confidence and participation."*

T11: *"... If it is necessary, the individual takes responsibilities that he/she can fulfill. It means talking, writing, reading, role playing, and participating in the activities. It means the learner is at the center, and teacher is the guider."*

T16: *"It means that student is provided with necessary opportunities he/she needs in the teaching process, and the student is making an effort to learn."*

T17: *“Active student means participating in the lesson, asking questions, answering questions even the answer is wrong, questioning his/her knowledge by asking “why, how”. It means practicing what it is learned in real life and reach to the conclusion by following clues.”*

T20: *“It means participating in the activities directly.”*

T22: *“Participating in the activities, having responsibilities in the activities. I think that students learn better by practicing and experiencing.”*

T27: *“It means student has interest in the lesson and shows his/her interest by participating in the lesson.”*

T30: *“Participating in lesson, talking in the lesson, preparing for the lesson and asking questions, teaching the subject, fulfilling responsibilities on time, etc.”*

T33: *“Student centered. It means student know what, when, why, how to learn.”*

T34: *“Student who learns how to learn participates in the lesson. Student using knowledge is active in the lesson. This is how it should be.”*

T36: *“Preparing for the lesson, searching, evaluating, linking the subjects, participating actively in many lessons, sharing the information.”*

T38: *“The most important criterion is that feeling happy in the classroom environment and being satisfied with learning are also make student active in the classroom.”*

According to teachers, active student feels comfortable, participates in the activities, talks in the classroom and asks questions, fulfills the responsibilities (homework, project, etc.) given about the lesson, is interested in the lesson. Apart from these teachers stated that students cooperate with his/her friends and teachers, decides about his/her studies, prepares for the lesson, takes responsibilities, talks, writes, reads about the lesson in teaching process, is interested in the lesson, feels comfortable in the classroom.

3.3. Teacher

Teacher theme was analyzed under following codes; features of teacher, supporting student, knowing student, attitude of teacher.

3.3.1. Features of Teacher

Opinions about what features teacher should have to make students active are as follows:

T1: *“Teacher should be a good performer, a good poet, a good musician. Teacher should use many methods and techniques while preparing the activities, and provide rich teaching learning environment.”*

T5: *“I make lessons enjoyable with some games (I write integers in 6 cards and divide students into groups, then ask them to order the numbers.).”*

T7: *"I try to care for students' features and interests to make the teaching process qualified. I teach lessons by considering students' readiness. I use activities in which students are active."*

T10: *"... Teacher should be qualified in his/her field. Teachers who know how to teach, who watch out individual differences in learning, and who have sufficient technic and equipment should conduct this learning process. Each student has individually different. The differences should be determined and education environment should be created according to these differences. Each student can be active when different methods and techniques are used."*

T11: *"First of all, student should like the lesson. If student is convinced about the importance of the lesson, he/she will be active."*

T12: *"Before starting the lesson, teacher should create an environment in which student can brainstorm so that the student will be active. Acting with the students together, and exchanging their ideas."*

T13: *"Making student participating in the lesson and finding appropriate methods and techniques makes student active."*

T17: *"Teacher should give students opportunity to find examples from their daily lives to make student active. After talking about the subject briefly, students should talk and give examples about the subject. Also, students should be encouraged to ask question and give answer."*

T19: *"I associate the lesson with daily life in order to teach students and take students attention, and I wait students to participate in the lesson."*

T20: *"Teacher should enrich the lesson with visual materials even with real objects."*

T26: *"Subjects should be interesting. If subjects are thought passively in teaching process, students' attention will decrease and they can't be active in the lesson. Different materials and activities should be used all the time. Student always should be curious about what will happen."*

T27: *"If subjects are adjusted according to student's level, we have experience successful education process. We increase student's confidence by giving them activities they can success. Thus, student's motivation will increase."*

T33: *"We can make students active by talking about the importance of the subject, why student should learn the subjects, and where the student can use his/her knowledge."*

T35: *"Students are at the center of teaching process, and teacher guide students in teaching process. In this atmosphere, students learn permanently."*

T37: *"Teachers definitely shouldn't act. A teacher who doesn't like his/her students is distinguished immediately. Teacher should know what he/she wants from students and act according to these demands."*

Teachers stated that a teacher should be a good performer, use different method and techniques, make lessons enjoyable, consider students' level, be qualified in his/her

field, know how to teach, endear lesson to students. Moreover, a teacher should consider students' opinions, use methods and techniques appropriate for student's age, give examples from students' daily lives, associate the lesson with daily life, enrich the lesson by using visual and real objects, and know what he/she wants from students.

3.3.2. Supporting Student

Teachers' opinions relating to supporting students are as follows:

T2: *"Giving responsibilities to students and give opportunity to practice the lesson."*

T4: *"Teacher should encourage students. To make this happen, teacher make student feel valuable."*

T7: *"Students should take responsibilities to be active in teaching process. Students' opinions about how the subject can be useful should be considered. Students are asked to associate previous subject and current subject. Students should be reminded the old subjects."*

T19: *"To make students active, active students should be appreciated. Students' attempts should be encouraged. Their mistakes should be corrected while correct answers are highlighted, it can be praised if necessary."*

T24: *"Students should take different responsibilities. Small gifts can be given to students. Competitive environment is allowed if students are successful."*

T27: *"Responsibilities and homework appropriate for students' age can be given."*

T36: *"Assigning tasks, distributing the subjects, rewarding successful student, guiding and showing ways to students."*

Teachers stated that it is important to give responsibilities, make students to have confidence, make them to feel valuable, help them to associate the old subjects with the new subjects, support students' attempts, highlight the correct answers while correcting the mistakes, phrase if necessary, give activities appropriate for students' level and they can success, reward students fulfilling his/her responsibilities.

3.3.3. Knowing Student

Teachers' opinions relating knowing students are as follows:

T23: *"Student doesn't participate in the lesson if he/she doesn't like or care. I talk with the student face to face and empathize with the student to solve the problem. I try to look the student's point of view; I don't force the student."*

T25: *"First of all, I have to know student and his/her family and then his/her life. I should choose the games and the jokes according to the student's understanding."*

T35: *"By following every student, encouraging students to participate in the lesson when they are ready, integrating students' interests and abilities with the lesson, talking with the students face to face."*

Teachers stated that they know students to endear the lesson, take students' attention, and know students, their families and their lives. Also, teachers think it is important to integrate students' interests and abilities with the lesson. Moreover, teachers sometimes talk with the students face to face.

3.3.4. Attitude of Teacher

Teachers' opinions relating attitude of teacher are as follows:

T1: *"Generally using the voice carefully, using intonation, asking questions about student's interest, calling students by their names can increase the motivation. Bu the important point is that teacher should make student believe that he/she can success. Teacher can make big changes in every teaching process. At the beginning of the lesson, aim of the subject and student's aim are associated, in this way; student can be active in the lesson."*

T6: *"I can make students active and focused by giving them responsibilities; I can take students' attention. When student realized that he/she could success, motivation and attitude will increase."*

T10: *"When student participate in the lesson, she/he can learn better. We can see that student learns better when we consider individual differences and teach."*

T16: *"Student is willing to learn if he/she needs that information and if the information is presented well. If student doesn't internalize the lesson, teacher should do something about it."*

T19: *"We try to see positive sides of other thoughts. When students are disrupted, I raise my voice and try to take their attention."*

T32: *"It shouldn't take long to teach. Teacher should use jokes and be funny while teaching. Practicing should take more space."*

T34: *"If student thinks that he/she is a part of the lesson, he/she will not be bored."*

Teachers stated that they call students by their name, make students feel like they can succeed and fulfill the responsibilities, consider individual difference, don't instruct too long, choose funny way to teach, consider practicing more. Moreover, students should feel that they are part of the lesson. These attitudes are important for students' success and motivation.

3.4. Supporting Permanent Learning

Teachers' opinions relating permanent learning are coded and analyzed under these terms: associating with real life, ways of supporting permanent learning, practicing and experiencing and repetition.

3.4.1. Associating with Real Life

Teachers stated that associating daily life with teaching process is very important. Opinions relating this issue are as follows:

T9: *"Using correct, daily, visual materials while teaching increases students' interest instead of directly teaching. As long as we support students' targeted attitude by teaching with daily examples, studying will be fun for students."*

T12: *"I don't want to be limited with the lesson I teach. I usually give examples from their daily lives to keep students active. When students get bored, I talk about different things that may get students' attention."*

T18: *"Associating the subject with daily life is not very hard for teachers. As long as students know the things they learn is not only in theory and they will be used in real life, students won't get bored in the lesson. Students learn dramatized real-life demo activities with fun and will. She/he can find a chance to use the information in real life."*

T19: *"We together associate the lesson with life, we discuss the lesson, we find and select different thoughts. Most of the time, we cannot reach a solution."*

Teachers stated that teaching with visual materials, giving examples from real life, associating subjects with daily life, getting the opportunity to use the knowledge in daily life is important for permanent learning.

3.4.2. Ways of Supporting Permanent Learning

Teachers' opinions relating to permanent learning are as follows;

T3: *"I teach new words and grammar before beginning the lesson. Later, I make students use these gestures in listening, reading and writing activities."*

T17: *"I support permanent learning by making them take notes, reviewing previous lesson, linking the subjects, rewarding students' success in front of the class, and hanging important structures to the wall."*

T19: *"I remind previous lesson and summarize the lesson at the end of the lesson. To be honest, I don't think I can support permanent learning and positive attitude as I have two lessons in a week. I give examples from the classroom, students, students' lives, I can support permanent learning."*

T6: *"...I think that meaningful learning will occur if students work individually as a group and if they do their homework based on searching and questioning."*

T7: *"I use visual materials, songs, videos in my lesson to support permanent learning, and address different learning styles. I give homework that can help students to learn new things. I try to use activities that keep students active."*

T8: *"I usually give homework that helps students to practice what they learn in order to support permanent learning when students are not at the school."*

T24: *"By using more visual materials."*

T25: *"First, students are always rewarded. Later, they are rewarded from time to time. Good behaviors are rewarded by saying "well done, great, look how your friend behaves..." Positive behaviors and attitudes are always rewarded."*

T27: *“Positive behaviors are always supported and rewarded in order to support permanent behaviors.”*

T32: *“Practicing for students is very important. It is also important to endear the subject.”*

T37: *“Little responsibility can be helpful even they are not like homework. Habits should be praised for permanent learning.”*

Teachers stated that relating supporting permanent learning and increasing success they make students take notes, reward students, support them, embody the subject with examples, give little responsibility and homework to students, summarize the subjects and use materials.

3.4.3. Practicing and Transferring into Life

Teachers' opinions about practicing and transferring into life are as follows:

T1: *“Adopting as a life style transferring and using the information in real life means student is reminded that the information can be useful in real life.”*

T14: *“Child should use the information in real life. If she/he doesn't know how to use, teacher should help the student. If the child is taught he/she should drink water for his/her system, teacher should control the child in breaks whether he/she drink water.”*

T16: *“A student who learns by practicing and experiencing and adopts the knowledge she/he learns takes the first step for permanent learning. Repeating what she/he learns support permanent learning after some time.”*

T18: *“Ability to transfer information into real life shows that student internalize the information. This learned information takes some time to turn into behavior. It should be supported.”*

T23: *“I help students to use information they learn in order to support permanent learning. This way, I support funny and permanent learning.”*

T30: *“By evaluating students, making them practice the information they can use, informing students about evaluation.”*

T31: *“By giving opportunities to practice, repeating frequently, and taking feedbacks.”*

T35: *“By observing students whether they use information, habits or attitudes in real life. I want students to write their knowledge and attitude from time to time. I follow their ability to listen, speak, write and read.”*

Teachers stated that it is important for students to adopt information as a life style and to use information in their life. Also, they stated that repeating frequently, observing students whether they use information, habits and attitudes in their life.

3.4.4. Repeating

It is understood that teachers use repeating to support permanent learning. Related opinions are as follows:

T1: *“Teacher can repeat old subjects if it’s necessary. Repeating frequently, studying, and evaluating support permanent learning.”*

T4: *“Solving questions, solving questions in every level, repeating important subjects support permanent learning.”*

T5: *“I distribute tests after the unit is over. I control homework I give one by one and I take notes on the chart.”*

T7: *“I talk about old subjects in order to link the old ones to the new ones. I teach in a way that students can be interested in order to support permanent learning. I arrange group works if the subject is suitable.”*

T9: *“Permanence occurs only with repeating and practicing.”*

T10: *“We support permanent learning by repeating frequently, making students use information in real life. Methods and techniques we use, the way we teach, our relationship with students are effective.”*

T11: *“The information students learn should be repeated. Knowledge that is not used in real life, unfortunately, won’t be permanent.”*

T12: *“Repeating my biggest sun. I always and in every minute repeat and make student practice.”*

T13: *“We can support permanent learning by repeating and linking information students learn.”*

T20: *“Students grasp what they are taught. But they have hard times to continue. To make them continue, I use activities they can repeat what I taught. It takes a lot of time to reach permanence, but students adopt information by repeating. In this way, students remember they learn and use in real life.”*

T28: *“By repeating the previous lesson, making students to resume what they are taught, summarizing and giving tests.”*

T38: *“I repeat the subjects about the lesson or different from the lesson to make students have knowledge, ability, and attitude.”*

Teachers stated that they repeat old subjects, repeat important subjects, give revision tests, and repeat a lot in every second in order to support permanent learning. Apart from this, they support permanent learning by repeating previous subject in every lesson, making students repeat what they are taught, and making them repeat the subjects they are taught or not.

3.5. Properties of Teaching Environment

Teacher opinions on *Properties of teaching environment* are a different subject than the other subjects and are an important one. Thus, it is analyzed as a single code.

3.5. Teaching Environment

Teachers' opinions relating teaching environment are as follows:

T8: *"There may be many activities to do about the issue. For me, creating an environment that keeps curiosity alive and separating the individual from the violence that he/she exposed."*

T14: *"I think an environment that keeps students away from pressure should be created to make students active. It is hard for students to be active if they don't want to be. We should make students want to be active. Lesson plans should be made by considering the place where students live, and economic situation should be considered to make students want."*

T16: *"The best way to make active students is to arrange environment for students' features by considering students' readiness and choosing methods and techniques according to the level of readiness."*

T18: *"Students will be active as long as they learn by practicing and experiencing, associate the information in real life, and are supported to learn. Will for participating in the lesson will increase when students understand information they learn is a part of the real life."*

T21: *"The best way to make active students is to arrange environment for students' features consider students' readiness, and choose methods and techniques according to the level of readiness. Qualified teaching process depends on qualified environment, qualified teachers and students."*

T32: *"Students are given opportunities to practice the subjects."*

T34: *"Students' confidence should be increased; teacher should praise everything students say so that they can feel their words are valuable."*

T38: *"...We should create environment in which students take little steps, can increase their confidence and feel that they can success. We should give them chance to make mistake so that they won't be afraid to make mistake. So, students won't be shy and will feel more comfortable while expressing themselves. Teachers should understand, guiding, supportive in such an environment."*

We understand from teachers' opinions an environment should keep alive curiosity, keep away students from situations that don't allow students to be active, support learning, is appropriate for students' features, and make students feel comfortable.

3.6. Method-Technique

Method-Technique was coded and analyzed under two themes: method-material and activity.

3.6.1. Method-Material

Teachers' opinions relating method-material are as follows:

T1: *"When students are taught with games, songs, and movements frequently, their motivation level increases. Also, using different techniques such as station, origami, dialogue activity, writing story and poem will be useful."*

T3: *"...When students watch movie, prepare performance project about different subjects, read book, they are more involved in the lesson. Speaking exam, I implement instead of normal exam, is different for the students; obligation to talk in English teach something to students."*

T6: *"If it is convenient to use in Science, alternative teaching methods such as doing experiment, doing projects, doing experiment as a group can be used, activities making students active."*

T7: *"Students' opinions should be taken about the subject by showing them visual to make them brainstorm. Students may be asked to research about the subject. Students should reach the information. They may share their findings in classroom."*

T8: *"I prefer using visual and audial materials that broaden the context of the lesson about the main subject."*

T11: *"By using role play, using visual materials, smart board, linking daily events with the history..."*

T13: *"To make the student active, it is necessary to address many sense organs. We must ensure that the student learns not only by hearing, but also by doing it. "*

T15: *"Students can keep their interests alive with multiple media, materials, and activities. Students should speak, move, and think in the lesson, not teachers "*

T17: *"I use more visual and audial material to keep the students interested in the classroom. I do opportunity trainings. If necessary, I will postpone the course to another time and teach according to their interest. The quality of education increases by using materials related to the lesson. Apart from these, experiments, observation studies, practicing and experiencing methods also make education more qualified. It should also not be forgotten that the biggest piece of qualified education is game "*

T19: *"My methods to increase the quality changes according to the level of the class. Reasoning and discussion are effective in some classes. I make them active, enjoy and teach the lesson. I use smart board if students like to be taught with presentations."*

T22: *“Drama, game, movie, research, etc. should be used. A material which take students’ interest relating to the subject... I believe that if teacher teach by using music, art and game, students’ interest will increase.”*

T26: *“I use different materials. Children like to play games and learn while playing. That’s why; I use games to make learning level at the highest point.”*

T28: *“I use different methods in lesson. Every child is different one another. So, different methods and materials should be used to draw students’ attention. Teaching is performing for me. By performing well....”*

T30: *“By using materials appropriate for the environment, using different methods (using practicing and experiencing, observing, telling etc. methods).”*

T34: *“I make them learn by practicing and experiencing. I make them learn with games.”*

T36: *“By preparing before the lesson, using visual, audial videos, making students to learn feeling like it’s their responsibility or role, using drama, groups work, case study etc. effectively.”*

T38: *“Class environment should be arranged for me for a qualified teaching process. We should use visual materials in the classroom. I want students to learn by practicing and experiencing, by making arrangements for students to provide their learning. I adjust some methods and techniques in activities such as educational games, case study, show-tell-do-apply, demonstration, experiment, question-answer, brainstorm.”*

We can understand from teachers’ opinions watching movie together, giving performance work, doing experiments individually, using role play, discussion, games, research, groups work, case study, educational games, show-tell-do-apply, experiment, question-answer, brainstorm should be used in teaching process. It is stated here that teachers should depend on only one method; he/she should use different methods and techniques. Moreover, teachers expressed that they use different visual and audial materials appropriate for the environment, smart board.

3.6.2. Activity

Teachers’ opinions relating to what kind of activities teachers should use to increase quality in education are as follows:

T5: *“Activities appropriate for the subject should be found. 5th grade students are wanted to bring leafs in different sizes before teaching field measurement. We want them to put their leaves on chequered paper and draw it outside. Then, they count the squares inside the figure.”*

T6: *“I choose activities appropriate for students’ age. Apart from these, I arrange lesson plan according to the subject.”*

T7: *“I want students to give examples about the subject from daily life. I try to make them curious. We watch videos and listen songs about the subject. I find games including vocabulary they are responsible, and I use these games in my lesson. I ask questions to students*

with low success so that they can participate in the lesson. I use visuals. I arrange group activities so that students can share information with their friends."

T8: *"I like to emphasize skill linking activities (reading, thinking critically, and writing), because students like to create something by themselves even they are not aware of it. This increases learning and supports permanence."*

T9: *"...I prefer to use activities with visual materials relating to targeted achievement. I want students to prepare presentation at the end of the subject and create a product."*

T14: *"Small stories, competitions, rewards, little experiments, and learning the relation between like and the subject they learn make students more willing."*

T15: *"I try to find activities that students enjoy. Games, role play, puzzle... I evaluate in every aspects. I consider not only exam results but also projects, books that students read, writing works. I always try to speak English. I answer in English even they ask question in English. I conduct quizzes apart from written exams."*

T16: *"On my own behalf, I find activities which are funny and they can do. When they succeed in this way, they want to do harder activities."*

T26: *"I try to affect students by teaching subjects in a way they like (stories, puzzles, and tongue twisters). If subjects and activities are associated, students spend quality time and learn quickly."*

T29: *"By taking care of all students in every activity since the number of students is low... By preparing activities that take their attention, communicating with all students since the number of students is low."*

T35: *"Doing activities that make students curious and direct them to search makes students active in teaching process. When students learn by practicing and experiencing, and involve in activities they can learn information which can be used in real life, students will be more active."*

T36: *"Social activities, games, wall newspaper, meeting with parents, activities, etc."*

T37: *"Sightseeing activities, conferences, activities which students can choose and contribute to education."*

T38: *"I try to make students more willing by giving activities which they can succeed and feel success. I also try to use activities (chosen according to students' level) in which students participate actively. I specially use activities by using educational games."*

Teachers emphasized that activities that is appropriate for students' age, lesson's stage, have visual content and appropriate for the environment are important for teaching process. Moreover, teachers should find activities like sightseeing that students enjoy, can succeed, make students feel successful, students can choose. Also teachers should take care of all students and make students practice.

3.7. Restraining Student Activity

This section is very important and negative for students. It was analyzed as one code.

3.7.1. Restraining Student Activity

T1: *"Students who don't have interest and motivation don't participate in the lesson."*

T2: *"Teacher teaches only for the exams. Books and achievements should be rearranged for real life situations and needs."*

T3: *"For a student who is motivated for learning, second obstacle is the environment in which she/he isn't comfortable."*

T8: *"Loss of curiosity if the result of the pressure that student exposed. We cannot expect from a student losing his/her curiosity to be active in learning process."*

T18: *"Students have isolated environment in school. This situation causes students to feel suspicious about the education and to think that school is unnecessary. As long as students learn in an environment which is not isolated, he/she will be active."*

T36: *"Students don't adopt or implement attitudes in family as they do in school. This is a temporary situation or there are not many attitudes that they don't adopt. School, family environment, visual and audial materials should have similar achievements for students."*

We can understand from teachers' opinions that students who aren't motivated don't participate in lesson, books and achievement should be arranged according to students' needs and lives, students don't have environment where they can feel comfortable, family doesn't raising style similar to school's achievements.

4. Result and Discussion

Increasing the quality of the teaching process depends on teacher, student, educational environment, teaching methods and techniques used materials, activities, etc. This research was carried out by taking teachers' opinions as the most influential factor of the learning outputs which emerged at the end of the teaching process. In this study, data collected from 38 teachers were analyzed by content analysis and findings were interpreted under seven themes: motivation, active students, teachers, supporting permanent learning, features of educational environment, method technique and restraining student activity.

Teachers expressed their opinions relating motivation for lesson under the motivation theme: Teachers try to increase or maintain the interest towards the lesson by endearing the lesson, doing appropriate activities, keeping alive their interest with different materials and giving interesting samples from daily life. In study of Arıkıl and Yorgancı (2012), it is stated that teachers use more activities to motivate students. Strategies that teachers use have positive effect on students (Görgen, Kömür, Deniz,

2009). Teachers expressed that they were trying to provide motivation by making students feel that they are valuable as individuals, changing methods, making students feel successful, rewarding, providing a comfortable learning environment and endearing the lesson. Literature shows that students' interest, participation, motivation and success have strong relation with students' motivation (Buchanan, Harlan, Bruce, and Edwards, 2016). Similarly, in study of Vatansever-Bayraktar (2015), supporting students, using different methods, rewarding, features of environment etc. provide to students' motivation. Teachers stated that they use activities, grades, daily and interesting problems, and choosing the student of the month when teachers rewarding students. Dilekmen (2008) expressed that students are needed to be rewarded by their teachers. This need is not only about the lesson; students are needed to be rewarded for their positive attitude and behaviors. Yaman and Güven (2014) suggested that when rewards, terminal, appropriate and positive behaviors are occurred, reward should be given immediately and the reason why the reward is given to student should be expressed clearly.

Active student is described as students participating activities, asking questions in the classroom, is interested in the subject, preparing before attending the lesson, feeling happy in the classroom. Doğan (2011) states that making students active and making them participate in activities are effective for students to gain confidence and sense of responsibility. Turkish education system was changed in 2005-2006; it adopted constructivist curriculum, introduced student-centered education, multiple intelligence approach (focusing on searching, questioning and discussing apart from reading and listening). Teachers stated their opinions relating features of teacher to improve quality in education. According to these opinions, teachers should use many different methods and techniques, consider students' level, be qualified in their fields, know how to teach, endear the lesson, take into account students' opinions, associate daily life with the lesson, and enrich the lesson with materials. Şahin (2011) stated in a study, called effective teachers' behaviors in terms of teachers' perception, that teacher should have enough knowledge about his/her fields, be a role model for students and environment, prepare for the lesson, consider individual differences of students, know students, love students. In study of Maden, Durukan, Aslan (2010) for Turkish teachers candidates some features of teachers are listed such as; having knowledge about his/her field, planning the lesson according to students' needs and interests, making Turkish lesson interesting and funny by associating the lesson with real life, caring for students, being happy, knowing their students and calling them by their names. According to Skourdoumbis (2017), the term of quality of teacher is linked with good and effective teacher term, and a teacher should have the ability to implement teaching process, improve abilities, evaluate and prepare. Teachers think that giving responsibilities to

students, making feel students valuable, making students link subjects, supporting students' attempts, highlighting the correct answers while correcting the mistakes, giving students activities they can accomplish, rewarding students, fulfilling responsibilities.

In Dikmen's study (2006) conducted with nursing students, it is stated that social support level perceived from instructors and families positively affects academic success. In study of Yurtal and Yontar (2006), it is stated that offering opportunities that help students to take responsibilities in the classroom or creating environments can be helpful in improving the responsibility.

Teachers expressed their opinions about knowing students; they think that it is important to know students to endear the lesson, to take students' attention, to talk with students face to face to know them, to help them to show their interests and abilities in lessons. Sarier (2016) emphasizes that teachers make students internalize the lesson by arranging different learning processes according to their interests and needs. Lastly, teachers stated their opinions relating to attitude of teacher. To call students by their name, to make students feel they can fulfill assignments and responsibilities, to consider individual differences, follow a process which is fun and witty, to make students practice, ensure students feel like they are parts of the lesson are important in students' success and motivation.

The results of Geçer and Deryakulu (2004) indicate that a moderate positive and significant relationship between primary education, teacher closeness, attitude and motivation is significant, indicating that the attitude towards a student is important. Geçer ve Deryakulu's (2004) study Determining, positive and meaningful relationship between primary-teacher connection and attitude and motivation shows that teacher's attitude towards student is important in a way. Karadüz and Sayın (2015) express that calling students by their names motivate them. Results of Beyaztaş and Senemoğlu's (2015) study show that expectations teacher has relating to learning in education environment is one of the factors effective in adopting learning approach. Also endearing or not endearing himself/herself to students by communicating effectively has the same effect.

Teachers remarked the importance of linking the subjects and daily life relating supporting permanent learning. It is stated that using visual, daily materials, giving examples from real life, having chance to adopt and transfer to real life are important for permanent learning. In study of Arıklı and Yorgancı (2012), teacher candidates and teachers stated that it is important to associate real life with subjects.

Teachers participated in the study make students take notes, reward students, support them, embody the subjects with examples, give students little assignment and homework, make student summarize, and use materials to support permanent learning.

Tathioğlu and Korkmaz stated that if subjects don't draw students' attention, cause students to disrupt and if students aren't interested in subjects, the subjects taught will be forgotten quickly.

Teachers remarked that making students practice, helping students to use knowledge, habits and attitudes in real life are important for permanent learning. According to İlgar and Gülten (2013), trying to teach mathematics without associating real life makes hard the subject to be learned and understood.

Teachers stated that they should repeat old subjects, giving revision tests, repeating every second, repeating in the lesson or somewhere else to support permanent learning. Yurtbakan et al. (2016) determined that repeating subjects is important to support permanent learning. Savaş, Taş and Duru (2010) emphasize that repeating from time to time makes students ready for exams and makes students remember the subjects they learn. Teachers expressed their ideas relating to education environment. They stated that teachers should keep alive students' curiosity, protect students from pressure to make them active, encourage them to learn, and create environment appropriate to the students' features and in which students feel comfortable. As stated by Şensoy and Sağsöz (2015), if educational environments are regulated by paying attention to the physiological, psychological and social characteristics of students, it will be a positive contribution to their academic and social life.

According to teachers' opinions relating to method-technique, teachers should give such as performance assignments, make students do experiments individually, use methods and techniques such as drama, discussion, teaching with games, research, group work, case method, educational games, demonstration, experiment, question-answer, brain storming. However, they stated that teachers shouldn't depend on to a single method; they should use different methods and techniques. Memiş and Erdem (2013) emphasize the success of the methods depends on the characteristic of the learners, the spoken language in the environment in which the subjects is taught, economic and social situation, etc. Results of a study conducted with Anatolian highschool teachers by Demirkan and Saraçoğlu (2016) show that teachers don't use techniques such as six thinking hats, aquarium, circle, fishbowl, station, role playing, and some teachers feel insufficient while using brainstorm, role play, show-tell-do-apply and station techniques. Ultimately, teachers use different methods and consider students' interests and needs are required for effective teaching.

In addition, teachers emphasized that the quality of teaching process can be increased by using materials that students can both listen and watch, smart board, visual different materials suitable for environment. Kablan, Topan, and Erkan (2015) state that teaching with materials has a positive effect of academic success, according to

the results obtained from 57 studies conducted in Turkey (p.1635). Teachers emphasized the importance of activities which is appropriate to the student's age, the subject, and the environment. Teachers also stated that it is required to use activities that students can enjoy, is fun and applied, students can feel the success.

Restraining student's activity is a negative theme appearing as a result of the study.

Teachers' opinions shows that there are some situations restraining students' activity: students with low motivation don't participate in the lesson, students who aren't in an environment they can express themselves, training in family isn't linked with school achievements. In the study of Kaya et al. (2005), called effect of negativities arising from classroom environment and accommodation problems on student' success, it is stated that crowded classroom, physical condition problems such as heat, light, noise decrease students' success.

To summarize the result of the study briefly, it can be understood that the environment in which students are valuable and students like their teacher was emphasized. Moreover, it has been stated that methods, materials and activities can be used diversely in learning teaching process. From this point of view, it can be suggested that different research methods (interview, observation, etc.), the teachers who are successful in the system and how teachers are supposed to teach to students in different level should be researched.

References

1. Arıkkıl, G., Yorgancı, B. (2012). Öğretmenlerin, Öğretmen Adaylarının ve Öğrencilerin Motivasyonu Algılama Farklılıkları. X. Ulusal Fen Bilimleri ve Matematik Eğitimi Kongresi, 27-30 Haziran 2012, Niğde Üniversitesi, Eğitim Fakültesi. Online: http://kongre.nigde.edu.tr/xufbmek/dosyalar/tam_metin/pdf/2389-30_05_2012-15_25_14.pdf (Erişim tarihi: 12.08.2017).
2. Azar, A. (2011). Türkiye'deki öğretmen eğitimi üzerine bir söylem: nitelik mi, nicelik mi?. *Yükseköğretim ve Bilim Dergisi*. 1(1) 36-38. DOI: 10.5961/jhes.2011.004.
3. Beyaztaş, İ. ve Senemoğlu, N. (2015). Başarılı öğrencilerin öğrenme yaklaşımları ve öğrenme yaklaşımlarını etkileyen faktörler. *Eğitim ve Bilim*. 40(179), 193-216. DOI: 10.15390/EB.2015.4214.
4. [Buchanan, Shelly](#), Harlan, Mary Ann, [Bruce, Christine S.](#), & [Edwards, Sylvia L.](#) (2016) Inquiry based learning models, information literacy, and student engagement: A literatüre review. *School Libraries Worldwide*, 22 (2), 23-39.

5. Creswell, J. W. (2005) *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research (2nd ed.)*. N.J.:Pearson Merrill Prentice Hall.
6. Demirkan, Ö. ve Saraçoğlu, G. (2016). Anadolu Lisesi öğretmenlerinin derslerde kullandıkları öğretim yöntem ve tekniklerine ilişkin görüşleri. *The Journal of International Lingual, Social and Educational Sciences*, 2(1), 1-11.
7. Dikmen, Y. (2016).Hemşirelik öğrencilerinde akademik başarının yordayıcısı olarak algılanan sosyal düzeyi ile yalnızlık arasındaki ilişkinin incelenmesi. *Journal of Human Sciences*, 13(2), 3033-3043. Doi:10.14687/jhs.v13i2.3790
8. Dilekmen, M. (2008). Etkili eğitim için etkili öğretmenlik. *Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 12(2), ss.214-220.
9. Doğan, Y. (2011). Fen ve teknoloji derslerinde yapılması öngörülen yapılandırmacı etkinliklerin uygulanma sıklığı, *Kuramsal Eğitimbilim*, 4 (1), 18-37.
10. Geçer, A. ve Deryakulu, D. (2004). Öğretmen yakınlığının öğrencilerin başarıları, tutumları ve güdülenme düzeyleri üzerindeki etkisi. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim*, sayı: 40, 518-543.
11. Görgeç, İ., Kömür, Ş., Deniz, Ş. (2009). İngilizce öğretmen adaylarının güdüleme stratejilerini değerlendirmeleri, *Muğla Üniversitesi sosyal bilimler enstitüsü dergisi (İLKE)*, 23, 147-160.
12. İlgar, L. ve Gülten, D. Ç. (2013). Matematik konularının günlük yaşamda kullanımının öğrencilere öğretilmesinin gerekliliği ve önemi. *İstanbul Sabahattin Zaim Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, Sayı:3,119-128
13. Kablan, Z., Topan, B. ve Erkan, B. (2015). Sınıf içi öğretimde materyal kullanımının etkililik düzeyi: bir meta-analiz çalışması, *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Bilimler*, 13(3), 1629-164.
14. Karadüz, A. ve Sayın, H. (2015). Öğretmenlerin derslerindeki konuşma edimlerinin öğrencileriyle iletişimlerine etkisi. *Turkish Studies International Periodical for the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 11(11), 883-908. DOI Number: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7827>.
15. Karasar, N. (2005) *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemi: kavramlar-ilkeler-yöntemler*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım.
16. Kaya, E., Bal, D.A., Sezek, F. ve Akın, M. (2005). Sınıf ortamı ve barınma sorunlarından kaynaklanan olumsuzlukların öğrenci başarısı üzerine etkisi. *Erzincan Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 7 (2), 41-51.
17. Maden, S., Durukan, E. ve Aslan, A. (2010). Türkçe öğretmeni adaylarının öğretmen niteliklerine yönelik görüşleri. *Turkish Studies International Periodical For the Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*. 5(6),
18. Memiş, M. M. ve Erdem, M.D. (2013). Yabancı dil öğretiminde kullanılan yöntemler, kullanım özellikleri ve eleştiriler, *Turkish Studies-International*

- Periodical For The Languages, Literature and History of Turkish or Turkic*, 8 (9), 297-318, Ankara-Turkey
19. Sarier, Y. (2016). Türkiye’de öğrencilerin akademik başarısını etkileyen faktörler: bir meta-analiz çalışması. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 31(3), 609-627. DOI:10.16986/HUJE.2016015868.
 20. Savaş, E., Taş, S. ve Duru, A. (2010). Matematikte Öğrenci Başarısını Etkileyen Faktörler. *İnönü Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi* 11(1). 113–132.
 21. Seferoğlu, S. S. (2004). Öğretmen yeterlikleri ve mesleki gelişim. *Bilim ve Aklın Aydınlığında Eğitim*, Sayı: 58, 40-45.
 22. Skourdoumbis, A. (2017). Teacher quality, teacher effectiveness and the diminishing returns of current ucation policy expressions. *Journal for Critical Education Policy Studies*, 15(1), 42-59.
 23. Şahin, A. (2011) Öğretmen algılarına göre etkili öğretmen davranışları. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 12 (1), 239-259.
 24. Şensoy, S. A. ve Sağsöz, A. (2015). Öğrenci başarısının sınıfların fiziksel koşulları ile ilişkisi. *Ahi Evran Üniversitesi Kırşehir Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 16(3), 87-104.
 25. Tatlıoğlu, K ve Korkmaz, G. (2015). İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Okul Başarılarını Olumsuz Etkileyen Nedenlerin Belirlenmesine Yönelik Bir Araştırma (Konya Örneği). *Karatekin Edebiyat Fakültesi Dergisi (KAREFAD)* 6(6), 93-116.
 26. Türk Eğitim Derneği (TEDMEN), 2014 Eğitim Değerlendirme Raporu- Ankara, 2014 Değerlendirme Dizisi: 1., Online: <http://portal.ted.org.tr/yayinlar/2014-egitim-degerlendirme.pdf>, (Erişim Tarihi: 12.08.2017).
 27. Vatansever-Bayraktar, H. (2015). Sınıf yönetiminde öğrenci motivasyonu ve motivasyonu etkileyen etmenler, *TurkishStudies-International PeriodicalfortheLanguages, LiteratureandHistory of TurkishorTurkic*, 10 (3), 1069-1090.
 28. Yaman, E., & Güven, N. (2014). Öğrencilerin motivasyon düzeyine etki eden önemli bir kavram: Ödül ve ceza. *International Journal of Human Sciences*, 11(1), 1163-1177. doi: 10.14687/ijhs.v11i1.2782.
 29. Yıldırım, A. ve Şimşek, H. (2008). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri*. Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.
 30. Yurtal, F. ve Yontar, A. (2006). Sınıf öğretmenlerinin öğrencilerinden bekledikleri sorumluluklar ve sorumluluk kazandırmada kullandıkları yöntemler. *Ç.Ü. Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 15 (2), 41-424.
 31. Yurtbakan, E. Aydoğdu-İskenderoğlu, T. ve Sesli, E. (2016). Öğrencilerin matematik dersindeki başarılarını artırma yolları konusunda sınıf öğretmenlerinin görüşleri. *Ondokuz Mayıs Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 35(2), 101-119. doi: 10.7822/omuefd.35.2.7.

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